

Appendix B: Additional figures

Fig. B.1: Column density and deuterium fractionation of N_2H^+ and ammonia. *First column:* Distribution of column density of N_2H^+ (blue) and N_2D^+ (green) from CASSIS MCMC calculation (1000 last steps). *Second column:* Distribution of deuterium fractionation derived from the MCMC column density distributions. *Third and fourth columns:* Same as for the first two columns, but for ammonia. Note the logarithmic axis for ammonia deuteration. Each pair of frames is for one source as indicated in the top right corner of the right frame. The sources are ordered along the North-South direction.

Fig. B.2: Spectrum map of the Junction region with the results of the infall diagnostics. Each frame of the map shows the local HCO^+ spectrum in grey, the N_2H^+ spectrum in black scaled by a factor of 4 for readability, and the Gaussian fit to the N_2H^+ spectrum in red. The N_2H^+ line shown in this Figure corresponds to the $F1F \rightarrow F'1F' = 01 \rightarrow 12$ transition (the isolated component). The vertical blue line shows the systemic velocity estimated from the peak of the Gaussian fit. The rms error (in km s^{-1}) and S/N of the N_2H^+ spectrum are indicated in the top-left corner, and the pixel number and value of δV_{HCO^+} are shown in the top-right corner. Top-left: colourmap of the δV_{HCO^+} values. One tile corresponds to one spectrum. Points with unreliable values are marked with a red cross. Bottom-right: histogram of the distribution of the obtained δV_{HCO^+} values. Points with unreliable values are indicated.

Fig. B.3: Parameters from NH₃ analysis: (1,1) line width, (1,1) and (2,2) peak temperatures as functions of ¹²CO, ¹³CO, C¹⁸O, CS and N₂H⁺ peak temperatures. The grey line denotes the least square fit slope with the Pearson r and p-values for each fit. Squares and circles show values for the first and second component, respectively. The error bars for ¹²CO, ¹³CO, C¹⁸O, CS and N₂H⁺ peak temperatures are the rms values given in Table 1.

Fig. B.4: Parameters from NH₃ analysis: kinetic temperature, gas pressure ratio and virial parameter as functions of ¹²CO, ¹³CO, C¹⁸O, CS and N₂H⁺ peak main beam temperatures. The grey line denotes the least square fit slope with the Pearson r and p -values for each fit. Squares and circles show values for the first and second component, respectively. The error bars for ¹²CO, ¹³CO, C¹⁸O, CS and N₂H⁺ peak temperatures are the rms values given in Table 1.

Appendix C: Deep spectra

Fig. C.1: Spectra of the observations on 1448, 1451, 1453 and 1454. The red and green vertical lines denote the velocities of the NH_3 (1,1) first, stronger and second, weaker components, respectively. As for 1454, the northern clump was mapped in N_2H^+ only using the FTS autocorrelator, hence the lower resolution. In addition, it was not included in the N_2D^+ , $o\text{-NH}_2\text{D}$, CH_3OH , and SiO measurements.

Appendix D: Ammonia analysis results

Table D.1: Results of the fit values with their uncertainties obtained from MC modelling (see Section 3.1.1 and 3.1.4). (1) Source name (2) components (3-10) (1,1) parameters and standard deviations: antenna temperature times tau, line velocity, FWHM, tau, (11-12) $\text{NH}_3(1,1)$ temperature

		$\text{NH}_3(1,1)$									
Source	C	$T_A \times \tau$ [K]	$\delta T_A \times \tau$ [K]	$v_{(1,1)}$ [km s ⁻¹]	$\delta v_{(1,1)}$ [km s ⁻¹]	Δv [km s ⁻¹]	$\delta \Delta v$ [km s ⁻¹]	τ	$\delta \tau$	$T_{(1,1)}$ [K]	$\delta T_{(1,1)}$ [K]
1446	1	2.17	0.09	8.22	0.01	1.17	0.03	0.52	0.1	1.59	0.03
1453	1	4.55	0.18	8.79	0.01	0.58	0.02	1.07	0.13	2.36	0.04
1454	1	7.79	0.36	5.25	0.01	0.46	0.01	3.24	0.25	2.12	0.05
1448	1	2.99	0.13	7.93	0.01	0.79	0.02	1.45	0.15	1.46	0.03
1448	2	0.98	0.12	6.88	0.02	0.73	0.06	0.52	0.35	0.66	0.04
1450	1	3.45	0.15	7.22	0.01	1.02	0.03	1.07	0.13	2.00	0.04
1450	2	0.58	0.18	5.57	0.04	0.67	0.13	0.34	0.8	0.4	0.06
1451	1	2.06	0.08	6.03	0.01	0.92	0.02	0.36	0.11	1.57	0.03
1451	2	0.83	0.09	7.72	0.02	0.85	0.06	0.75	0.32	0.53	0.03

Table D.2: Results of the fit values with their uncertainties obtained from MC modelling (see Section 3.1.1 and 3.1.4). (1) Source name (2) components (3-8) (2,2) parameters: area, line velocity, FWHM, (9-10) (2,2) temperature

		$\text{NH}_3(2,2)$									
Source	C	A	δA [K km s ⁻¹]	$v_{(2,2)}$ [km s ⁻¹]	$\delta v_{(2,2)}$ [km s ⁻¹]	$\Delta v_{(2,2)}$ [km s ⁻¹]	$\delta \Delta v_{(2,2)}$ [km s ⁻¹]	$T_{(2,2)}$ [K]	$\delta T_{(2,2)}$ [K]		
1446	1	0.45	0.02	8.21	0.03	1.41	0.08	0.45	0.02		
1453	1	0.16	0.02	8.73	0.03	0.66	0.08	0.33	0.04		
1454	1	0.13	0.01	5.22	0.02	0.57	0.05	0.3	0.02		
1448	1	0.22	0.03	7.89	0.05	0.83	0.12	0.37	0.05		
1448	2	0.14	0.03	6.91	0.07	0.76	0.17	0.25	0.05		
1450	1	0.31	0.02	7.18	0.04	1.05	0.1	0.41	0.03		
1450	2	0.05	0.02	5.61	0.17	0.71	0.39	0.1	0.94		
1451	1	0.18	0.02	6.01	0.05	1.03	0.11	0.25	0.02		
1451	2	0.17	0.02	7.75	0.09	1.51	0.21	0.16	0.02		

Table D.3: Results of the Python refit of CLASS values with their uncertainties obtained from MC modelling. (1) Source name (2) components (3-6) (1,1) parameters and standard deviations: kinetic and excitation temperature (7-10) NH_3 column density, H_2 volume density (11-16) thermal line width, non-thermal line width, gas pressure ratio (17-18) virial parameter

Source	C	T_{kin} [K]	δT_{kin} [K]	T_{ex} [K]	δT_{ex} [K]	N_{tot} [cm^{-2}]	δN_{tot} [cm^{-2}]	$n(\text{H}_2)$ [cm^{-3}]	$\delta n(\text{H}_2)$ [cm^{-3}]	Δv_{th} [km s $^{-1}$]	$\delta \Delta v_{th}$ [km s $^{-1}$]	Δv_{nt} [km s $^{-1}$]	$\delta \Delta v_{nt}$ [km s $^{-1}$]	R_p	δR_p	α	$\delta \alpha$
1446	1	17.25	0.50	6.64	0.76	6.88e+14	1.27e+14	1.13e+04	3.55e+03	0.216	0.003	1.153	0.026	0.035	0.002	0.367	0.016
1453	1	12.12	0.45	6.33	0.30	7.06e+14	7.96e+13	1.36e+04	1.81e+03	0.181	0.003	0.552	0.016	0.108	0.007	0.072	0.004
1454	1	9.96	0.23	4.93	0.07	1.92e+15	1.45e+14	7.94e+03	3.44e+02	0.164	0.002	0.434	0.015	0.143	0.010	0.030	0.002
1448	1	14.32	0.80	4.63	0.12	1.26e+15	1.18e+14	5.02e+03	3.81e+02	0.197	0.005	0.763	0.023	0.067	0.005	0.212	0.012
1448	2	20.45	3.07	4.34	2.92	4.48e+14	2.42e+14	3.60e+03	4.52e+04	0.235	0.017	0.687	0.060	0.118	0.027	0.180	0.029
1450	1	13.85	0.47	5.77	0.28	1.21e+15	1.37e+14	9.34e+03	1.17e+03	0.194	0.003	0.997	0.026	0.038	0.002	0.098	0.005
1450	2	16.72	6.03	4.13	2.51	2.54e+14	1.18e+15	3.29e+03	1.60e+04	0.213	0.063	0.634	0.139	0.113	0.214	0.042	0.018
1451	1	13.86	0.54	7.95	2.67	3.62e+14	1.03e+14	2.20e+04	5.52e+04	0.194	0.004	0.897	0.022	0.047	0.003	0.214	0.010
1451	2	16.97	1.31	3.74	1.79	7.11e+14	2.65e+14	2.30e+03	7.75e+03	0.215	0.008	0.826	0.061	0.068	0.010	0.184	0.026

Appendix E: MCMC corner plots of N_2H^+ , N_2D^+ , and NH_2D spectra

Fig. E.1: Corner plots of the MCMC fitting of N_2H^+ spectra. The top row shows the characteristics of the two components of the source 1446, and the second row for the two components of source 1448. In each frame, the top right part shows the observed spectrum in blue and the best χ^2 model in orange, for the sum of the two components. The acceptance rate is also represented. For both sources, ten independent Markov chains were stacked to maximise the sampling of the parameter space.

Fig. E.2: Same as Fig. E.1 but for sources 1450 (top row), 1451 (middle row), and 1453 (bottom row). For 1453, only one Markov chain is represented because the ten chains were very similar.

Fig. E.3: Same as Fig. E.1 but for N_2D^+ spectra.

 Fig. E.4: Same as Fig. E.1 but for NH₂D spectra.

Appendix F: Infall maps

Fig. F.1: Overview of the infall diagnostics of the G202 area. *Left*: colourmap of the δV_{HCO^+} values for an extended area compared to Fig.B.2 One tile corresponds to one spectrum. Points with unreliable values are marked with a red cross. *Top right*: pixels used to compile the spectra map shown on the N_2H^+ integrated intensity map. *Bottom right*: histogram of the distribution of the obtained δV_{HCO^+} values. Points with unreliable values are indicated. The tiles whose spectra are not shown in Fig. B.2 are shown in Fig. F.2.

Fig. F.2: Details of the infall diagnostics of the southern compact sources and the additional points above the chosen S/N threshold in the G202 area. *Top and Middle rows:* Spectra (left) and colourmap of the δV_{HCO^+} values (right) of the two southern compact sources visible in Fig. F.1: the southeast compact source (top) and the southwest compact source (middle). *Bottom row:* spectra of the additional points above the chosen S/N threshold.